

PECULIARITIES OF IDIOMATIC COMPOUND NOUNS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551374>

Qahorov Maqsud Usmon o'g'li

2nd-course student

Masters department

Uzbek State World Languages University

Annotation. *This article is about the examination of semantic idiosyncrasies of to some extent informal compound words in the English and Uzbek languages through investigation. A review explored the degree to which English compound things are hazardous for students of English as a subsequent language and recognize certain purposes of this appreciation trouble. Subjects were college understudies, of generally changing language foundations, in courses in English for scholarly purposes. Each was managed by an instrument planned to quantify cognizance of both genuine and designed English compound things. For each compound thing, the scope of potential definitions, including distractors, was advertised. Results recommend that the perception of some compound things is tricky because their colloquial and syntactic mistiness, without culture-explicit logical information, obliges the distinguishing proof of erased components. In any case, when the student has adequate openness to the language, these troubles are defeated promptly. There is likewise proof that students utilize allegorical procedures in managing idiomaticity. It is reasoned that appreciation issues looked at by students of English as a subsequent language experiencing compound things might be very like those looked at by local speakers.*

Keywords: *metaphor; semantics; full, partial idiomaticity; compound words; explicit, implicit, and pattern meanings.*

Introduction. The development of compound words isn't just the blend of two parts, yet additionally, it is the consequence of a complex process. As per E. S. Kubryakova, the semantics of any inferred word is more than the amassing of sememes of its constituents. There are sure covered-up implications in the semantic structure of determined and compound words which assume a fundamental part in local speakers' discourse. On the off chance that there are no such deeper implications in local speakers' talking potential, this word becomes a misconception in this case. That implies the presence of idiomaticity in such compound words. Following A. I. Smirnitsky who characterized the peculiarity of idiomaticity as "the cycle which isn't the outcome of the blend of all broad

sememes," we can express that any determined or compound word should insight (go through) the peculiarity of idiomaticity to certain broaden. The significance of word arrangement design is a piece of the semantics of a given word. To demonstrate our thought the accompanying can be exemplified: book shop - "one, who sells books" is a compound word and its semantics incorporates "one", "who" which are helper words, - "s" third individual solitary and predicative connection in its change. As this method of word development is connected with language, yet isn't communicated verifiably in the compound word we restrictively call is as "syntactic idiomaticity". We need to examine the portrayal of idiomaticity which is one of the most real issues of the current day phonetics, furthermore its acknowledgment in compound words in English and Uzbek languages. [1]

Various elements of compound words in English have been contemplated by H. Marchand, A. I. Smirnitsky, O. D. Meshkov, A. V. Arnold, I. Ibragimkhodjayev, compounding in Uzbek have been concentrated by Sh. Rahmatullayev, A. Khodjiyev, B. Madariyev, N. Mamatov, the issues of the arrangement of compound words, their morphological arrangement, semantics, their distinction from word blends, the orthography of compound words have been portrayed in the progress of previously mentioned creators. Be that as it may, the issues of the semantics of compound words, their express, certain and design implications which came about because of constituent parts of the given compound words, the issue of compound words having a place with which sort of arrangement regardless of whether they have a place with structure or semantic sort need further examination. As the compound words are not being examined according to semantic perspective, the job and spot of compounding in word-building are as yet unclear. The spot of colloquial compound words in English and Uzbek in the word arrangement framework is equivocal. As the investigations of models show that from a semantic point the parts of colloquial compound words are blended such a lot that they are viewed as the entire unit, a separate lexeme much of the time. It is generally expected information that the interest in accumulating words depends on naming things. The foundation of compound words normally depends on a semantic and syntagmatic mix of a few words. The informal compound words arise because of the solidarity of syntagm significance and language in talk as a rule. While managing compound words semantics there surely emerge the issues of congruity in importance and different solidarity of

¹ Смирницкий А. И. Лексикология английского языка. – М.: Издательство литературы на иностранных языках, 1956.

parts comprising the importance of the word, in addition, the example of a determined word is implied, and there show up a subjection (of head and modifier) came about because of the mix of two stems in a compound word. For example, the English compound word room (bed - 'a household item for rest or rest, ordinarily a system with a sleeping cushion', room - 'a section or division of a structure encased by dividers, floor, furthermore roof') comprising of two parts express an entirety meaning - "a space for staying in bed". The Uzbek compound word karvonboshi (karvon - 'a gathering, particularly dealers or explorers, bridging a desert' - bosh 'pioneer,') is the mix of two parts communicating a separate significance - an individual who is the top of the procession.

As is seen from the models, the mix of two stems structures a compound word with another significance. The term idiomaticity in etymology is now and again used to communicate phraseological units (V. V. Vinogradov, N. N. Amosova, A. V. Koonin what's more V. Teliya). To be specific, as per A. A. Reformatsky, idiomaticity is perceived as an overall allegorical significance that isn't come about because of the blend of the importance of parts of phraseological units, which can't in a real sense be converted into another language. Idiomaticity of expressions has been concentrated exhaustively in present-day phonetics yet it is the compound words that need profound investigation. This peculiarity is confined with general definitions in English whereas in Uzbek has not been examined alright. A. Smirnitsky, demonstrating the English compound word slate to be informal compound word comes to end that any writing board can't be the slate utilized in class as the chalkboard can be made of not just the wooden board, but, it can likewise be made of a synthetic substance, it is the object of instructing process: "when the general significance of a compound word isn't gotten from the collection of its parts, and it communicates one entirety idea it is a colloquial compound word". While exploring the issue of the informal compound word we are attempting to depict their particular highlights as expressed over this field of study has not been very much examined. Our examination uncovers that compound words can be isolated into full and halfway idiomaticity. [2]

After intensive investigations of compound words in English and Uzbek languages we chose to characterize the full colloquial compound word as the compound words whose all parts express non-literal importance, and halfway informal compound word is a compound word whose one of the parts can communicate non-literal. We will investigate a portion of the English and Uzbek

² Арнольд И. В. Лексикология современного английского языка. – М.: Высшая школа, 1986.

full colloquial compound words beneath. The Uzbek compound word Boltayutar (Болтаютар) (bolta - a hatchet; and yutar - to swallow) can be a model for a full informal compound word. The word reference meaning of the parts of this compound word isn't viewed as here as it implies a flying predator which eats dead bodies. The English compound word Brain-channel - "the migration of researchers, technologists, talented specialists and so forth for better compensation, hardware or conditions" can be a model for a full informal compound word in English. The main part of this compound word has gone through the metonymic transaction, where the subsequent part encountered an allegorical change because of which the two parts have lost their unique essential importance. The words utilized as a part of a colloquial compound word can lose their essential significance, or turn into a theoretical thought it might turn into

a method for semantic changes. Contrasting from full idiomaticity, in the halfway informal compound words one component of this unit can have moved significance while the other part safeguards its denotative meaning. For instance, the Uzbek compound word pakhtaolma (пахтаолма) (pakhta - cotton; olma - an apple) is a sort of early maturing apple. The principal part of this compound word has informal significance acclimatized with cotton as this sort of apple is milder than different kinds of the apple. Another model can be Qo'ytikan (Қўйтикан) (Qo'y - sheep; tikan - thistle) which is a plant for certain thistles on its organic product. The part thistle (tikan) has saved its denotational meaning while the other part qo'y is utilized allegorically. Here, the element of this plant which it can regularly be found on the assemblage of sheep is considered. Qo'qonarava (Қўқонарава) is a truck with two major wheels where the second part arava (a truck) has safeguarded its word reference meaning while the primary part qo'kon has encountered allegorical transaction.

Throughout the entire existence of Uzbekistan, such enormous wheeled trucks were delivered in Kokand, which were truly agreeable for sloppy roads. The Uzbek compound word Bobotil (Боботил) (bobo - granddad; until - a language) is a language of old precursor. There is an incomplete idiomaticity in this word where the part language (or tongue) protects its denotational significance while the other part "bobo" (granddad) has gone through an allegorical change. There is a shape cockscomb in the Uzbek compound word Gultojikhuroz (Гултожихўроз) (gul - a blossom; toj-a cockscomb, or a crown; khuroz - a cockerel, chicken). "Khuroz" (хўроз) is utilized as a trait that communicates not the lords' or alternately sovereigns' crown, yet it is rooster's brush. Additionally, there is the word 'gul' (a blossom) in the compound word

which gives the overall significance of the word (the name of a plant is created by the blend of all parts). The Uzbek compound word Khurozqand (Хўрозқанд) (khuroz - a chicken, a chicken; qand - candy) suggests the candy in state of a rooster arranged for kids in general. Indeed 'Khurozqand' is made in other various shapes (for example rectangular, three-sided, round shape; not in a state of the rooster) it is called Khurozqand. Several such models can be viewed in English too. Ferocious - a killer or other savage crook. The second part of this word "throat" has gone through a semantic change, by and by it assists with understanding the overall significance of the entire word. At the point when this word is converted into Uzbek it communicates 'tomoq kesuvchi' (томоқ кесувчи) (tomoq - throat; kesmoq - to cut), tomoq kesuvchi has changed into 'kallakesar' (kalla - ahead; kesar - cut). Eggplant - the huge egg-molded product of an Old World plant, eaten as a vegetable. Its skin is normally dim purple, however, the skin of specifically developed assortments is white or yellow. The primary part of this compound word "egg" is idiomaticity, shaped by absorption. Eggplant is utilized figuratively as it has an egg-like shape. ³

The subsequent part "plant" has protected its denotational meaning. Another compound word Footnote - an extra snippet of data printed at the lower part of a page, can be a model for a halfway colloquial compound word. The main part "foot" has a figurative change where the subsequent part safeguards its word reference meaning. The importance of the given compound words may not be founded on the importance of the parts comprising them. For example, a Frogman is an individual who swims underwater wearing an elastic suit, flippers, and an oxygen supply. The first part of this compound word "frog" has an allegorical significance associated with the frog's living in the water. Here, an individual plunging into the water with extraordinary suit and oxygen and performing his responsibility is acclimatized with a frog. The subsequent part of the compound word safeguards its essential importance. As the above-given models show the arrangement of incomplete colloquial compound words in languages being thought about depends on figurative and metonymic transactions. The investigated models clarify that the peculiarity of idiomaticity would be prudent to study in the circle of development of compound words after phraseological units. To concentrate on compound words from the mark of idiomatic and separating them into full and incomplete degrees offers a chance to gain the

³ Atajonova A. Modern Uzbek Literary Language (A Methodical Handbook for Academic Lyceum Students) - Tashkent: Bayoz, 2017. 178 pages.

semantics of compound words profoundly. Near examination of informal compound words in English and Uzbek which are non-kindred languages will be supportive in deciding the likenesses and contrasts of this issue and uncovering unseen pieces of this science. Alongside changes in the political, financial, and social circles, the peculiarity of word arrangement in semantics is additionally creating. Word development is the making of new lexical units in light of the material and conceivable outcomes accessible in the language. This cycle advances the substance of the language word reference consistently. One of the most generally utilized word frames today, which is viewed as all-encompassing and succinct, as well as useful, is compound words. Compound words are a vital and pertinent peculiarity for all languages.

These days, science and innovation are quickly advancing and we need to utilize compound words to advance new words that roll in from various languages, regardless of whether we like it or not. For instance, a plastic card, a Wi-Fi switch, etc. The compound word peculiarity E. A. According to Vasilevskaya, language is the keenest method for forming jargon content and linguistic design. In current Uzbek, compound words are additionally generally utilized: in scholarly, logical, philosophical, specialized, and rural works, in the media, as well as in live correspondence. The utilization of such compound words alone isn't sufficient, and issues emerge in understanding and deciphering them accurately. The majority of the new words and compound words that come into our language are in English. For instance, a cell phone, a cheeseburger, a playboy, etc. The English word formation framework has its etymological elements, and the investigation of the peculiarity of word formation as far as coordinated and diachronic times of language improvement has continuously been an effective issue. Remembering compound words for English requires unique consideration. Understanding them accurately and having the option to decipher and apply them is causing a part of the discussion. On the off chance that we intently check out the Uzbek language, a large portion of the new words have entered and are advancing our language from the English compound words with the requests of the times. A portion of these normal words are acknowledged without change: PlayStation 3, 4 - PlayStation 3, 4 (the name of the sort of game gadget that is associated with the TV and controlled utilizing exceptional control buttons) or Facebook - Facebook (one of the names of social destinations); a piece of it is framed by the mix of Uzbek words. For instance: ярим финал (semi-last), фото мухбир (photograph correspondent), and so forth For a right comprehension of these peculiarities, it is important to find replies to such inquiries as a compound word and what is its

inclination, what are the highlights of compound words in the English language. Therefore, to see such compound words accurately, a more profound investigation of the characteristics of Uzbek and English compound words is turning into a necessity of the time. The peculiarity of compound word development is important for morphology and manages word development. It is a strong method for improving jargon on an etymological scale, to make powerful utilization of existing lexical units, and to make meaning more compact.^[4]

Conclusion. It is important to take note that the investigation of lingua-social, orientation, realistic, talk and mental elements of the informal compound words expects to become familiar with their psycholinguistic, sociolinguistic, and reasonable semantic characteristics in the present-day phase of contemporary phonetics. So, word arrangement or shaping new words strategies in the cutting edge Uzbek language has been read up for quite a while prior and recognized unexpectedly. On the off chance that you look intently, piece or compounding (at least two words) in the Uzbek language is utilized in practically all writing and has been examined as a peculiarity. All things considered, a few etymologists prevent this reality on the premise of getting specific proof. Over the long run, mentalities towards this language peculiarity may likewise change. As we would like to think, there are various approaches to shaping words, including arrangement, similarly to different languages.

REFERENCES:

1. Реформатский А. А. Введение в языковедение. – М.: Аспект пресс, 2006.
2. Смирницкий А. И. Лексикология английского языка. – М.: Издательство литературы на иностранных языках, 1956.
3. Кубрякова Е. С. Язык и знание. – М.: Языки славянской культуры. 2004, – С. 393.
4. Арнольд И. В. Лексикология современного английского языка. – М.: Высшая школа, 1986.
5. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. 5-томлик. – Т.: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси нашриёти, 2006–2008.

⁴ Buranov J.B, Yusupov U.K, Iriskulov M.T, Sodikov A.S. The grammtical structure of English, Uzbek and Russian. Tashkent, Ukituvchi p1, 1986 p 308.

6. LONGMAN Dictionary of English Language and Culture. – London, 2006.
7. Arnold I.V. The English word, -1986. – 384 p.
8. AtajonovaA. Modern Uzbek Literary Language (A Methodical Handbook for Academic Lyceum Students) - Tashkent: Bayoz, 2017. 178 pages.
9. Bobojonov G., RajapovaK. Uzbek (basic knowledge) - Nukus. 2017.
10. Bodle A. How new words are born [Electronic resource]. – 2016. – Retrieved from:<https://www.theguardian.com/media/mind-yourlanguage/2016/feb/04/englishneologisms-new-words>